

**FOOD FOR
THE FUTURE**
NORTH YORKSHIRE

FOOD FOR THE FUTURE

NORTH YORKSHIRE:

A Framework for Action

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Foreword

We're living through challenging and unpredictable times - rising health inequalities, economic uncertainty, and the growing impact of climate change. In the middle of all this, our food system plays a bigger role than many people realise. It's not just about what's on our plates - it's about our health, our communities, our economy, and the environment. It's about making sure we are resilient to future challenges in food supply and making sure everyone has access to good food.

North Yorkshire's Food for the Future plan recognises that food connects to almost every part of our lives. It affects how healthy we are, how strong our local economy is, and how we care for the planet. But too often, these areas are looked at separately. That means we miss chances to make real, lasting change.

This framework brings everything together, looking at the whole food system. It's a joined-up plan that encourages teamwork between councils, the NHS, schools, farmers, businesses, researchers, and local people. It's about making sure that every part of our food system - from how food is grown to how it's eaten - supports healthier people, a cleaner environment, and a stronger local economy.

This isn't just another policy document. It's a call to action. A chance to rethink how we value food - not just as a product, but as something that can help our communities thrive and our environment recover.

Whether you're a decision-maker, a community leader, a business owner, or simply someone who cares about good food, we invite you to be part of this journey. This framework is a living tool - shaped by evidence, guided by local voices, and built on shared ambition.

Together, we can create a food system that works for everyone: where good food is available to all, where we waste less, work with nature, and support local jobs and businesses to grow.

This framework is ambitious, but I'm confident its goals can be reached. Its success will depend on a shared commitment to building something greater than the sum of its parts - a stronger, more sustainable, and resilient local food economy in North Yorkshire. Achieving this will take teamwork and a shared dedication to the principles in this plan. That means food producers growing in environmentally friendly ways, manufacturers, retailers and tourism businesses prioritising local supply chains, and the public sector playing its part by supporting local procurement.

Jan Thornton MBE
Vice Chair FixOurFood Commission

This framework for action clearly aligns with the objectives of the FixOurFood Research programme at the University of York. The framework will facilitate building a regenerative food system that creates positive outcomes in terms of environment and human health. This place-based approach will provide a template for other UK regions who believe in transformative food system change. Great to see North Yorkshire showing UK leadership here.

Professor Bob Doherty
FixOurFood Academic Director

Our local health and wellbeing strategy wants residents of North Yorkshire to have a fair chance of living a fulfilling life, free from preventable ill health, 'adding years to life and life to years'.

This Food for the Future framework recognises the importance that food plays in achieving this aim, and is a key building block in trying to reduce health inequalities. I would encourage everyone to look at the framework and see what part they can play to achieve the vision.

Councillor Michael Harrison
Executive Member for Health and Adult Services

The vision

Everyone has affordable, nutritious and sustainable food in North Yorkshire, for North Yorkshire.

Our framework for action

What is a food system?

A **food system** is the entire journey food takes from the moment it's produced to the moment it's eaten, thrown away or recycled. It includes everything from growing crops and raising animals, to processing and packaging, transporting, selling, cooking, eating, and dealing with leftovers or waste. But it's not just about the food itself. It's also about the people, places, and processes involved at every step - farmers, fishers, factory workers, lorry drivers, shopkeepers, chefs, and families at home.

In the UK, our food system touches nearly every part of daily life. It affects our health - what we eat can help prevent illness or contribute to it. It shapes our economy - millions of jobs depend on food, from agriculture to hospitality. And it has a huge impact on the environment - how we produce and consume food influences climate change, biodiversity, and the use of land and water.

Understanding food as a system helps us see the bigger picture. It shows how decisions in one area - like how we farm or what we import - can have knock-on effects elsewhere, such as on food prices, public health, or carbon emissions. By thinking in this joined-up way, we can work towards a food system that is fairer, healthier, and more sustainable for everyone.

A food system affects:

- Our health (e.g. access to nutritious food)
- Our environment (e.g. carbon footprint, land use)
- Our economy (e.g. jobs in farming, retail, hospitality)
- Societal fairness (e.g. ensuring everyone can afford good food)

Food for the Future North Yorkshire - a whole system approach

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The food system in North Yorkshire

ⁱOur county is the largest in England at 8,000 square kilometres (3,090 square miles) with over 615,400 people to feed. Agriculture, forestry and fishing account for as much as 20% of the regional market, and 78% of North Yorkshire’s land area is used for agriculture.

North Yorkshire has a strong food heritage and thriving innovation

North Yorkshire’s expansive farmland, rugged coastlines, and historic market towns produce some of the highest-quality food in the world.

We are home to an array of artisan producers, farm shops and delis, cafes, coffee shops, breweries, restaurants, and hotels – the highest concentration of food and drink businesses in the UK. We house innovative global brands such as McCains, Heck, Quorn, and Taylors of Harrogate – food and drink producers who contribute £3 billion in economic value to the regionⁱⁱ. North Yorkshire is one of England’s most important farming counties: agriculture has been a mainstay of the local economy for centuries, and the region is famous for its high-quality livestock and produce. Our strong food heritage and food innovation provide a brilliant foundation for transforming our food system across our land, ports and sea.

North Yorkshire has great strength in community food activity

Local groups benefit from food banks, social supermarkets, community fridges and community food-growing projects across the county. Holiday activity programmes (see [FEAST What is FEAST - North Yorkshire Together](#)) ensure children get fed in the holiday periods across the year, while free school meal auto-enrolment is in place to ensure anyone who is entitled to receive free school meals can easily gain access to them. Support and education are also available around food waste reduction, subsidisation of home composting and food digesters. Our Framework for Action builds on this community-focused activity and an ethos of looking out for those most in need.

North Yorkshire is innovating its food production and land management

There is activity across the county to re-wet peat bogs to proactively capture carbon and reduce flooding of farmland and downstream homes by storing rainwater. New kinds of livestock feed are being developed to reduce methane emissions, and farmers are being supported and connected to adopt more environmentally friendly practices. We can work with this inspiring innovation in our county’s land management to help transform our food system. But as the next section illustrates, we need to do much more.

ⁱ This map of the North Yorkshire district under jurisdiction of North Yorkshire Council, showing major land cover types, river systems and human settlements. The land use pixel scale is 1 km. Image produced by Juan Pablo Cordero and Sam J. Buckton using AgriFoodPy and QGIS. Based upon Land Cover Map 2023 © UKCEH 2024. Contains Ordnance Survey data © Crown Copyright 2007, Licence number 100017572.

Challenges in our food system

Despite North Yorkshire’s thriving food system innovation, heritage, and community focus, our food system also faces some big challenges.

Our health - Diet-related illness strains our health and care systems. A third of our children and 61% of adults are overweight or obeseⁱⁱⁱ, leading to a host of complications such as malnutrition, dental disease, cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular disease and dementia. Junk food is too readily available and too cheap. After housing costs, the poorest 20% UK households spend 74% of income to maintain a healthy diet^{iv}. Our rural communities spend higher amounts of disposable income on travel to access food and pay at a premium.

Remote and rural areas in North Yorkshire have the lowest levels of access to a food shop within 15 minutes by public transport or walking

- Department for Transport, [United Kingdom Food Security Report 2021: Theme 4: Food Security at Household Level - GOV.UK](#)

14% of households - an estimated 7.3 million adults, nationally, - were affected by food insecurity in January 2025

- Food Foundation [Latest food insecurity tracker shows seven million adults going hungry | Food Foundation](#)

What do we need to confront?

- Big players dominating supply chains.
- Smaller food organisations in North Yorkshire struggling with the capacity for big change.
- Mindsets across a convenient food system. Some people don’t want to change; others don’t know how to.
- Substantial carbon emissions across the food system.
- Threats to our food security and resilience from climate change.
- National policy, geo-politics, and the impact of conflicts across the globe restricting local influence and power.
- Anxiety and worry across the system, in our farmers, producers, in food citizens. Climate anxiety in young people as an increasingly serious issue.

Our economy – The UK gets most of its food from a mix of home-grown produce and international trade, with about 60% coming from domestic sources and 40% from abroad. However, extreme weather is having increasingly detrimental impacts on UK farming - especially crops like grains, fruits, and vegetables.

Global events have also disrupted food supply. For example, Russia’s invasion of Ukraine in 2022 caused major interruptions in the trade of key crops like cereals and oilseeds, leading to sharp price increases.

When it comes to fruits, vegetables, and seafood - important sources of vitamins and minerals - the UK relies heavily on imports.

Many of the countries supplying these foods are facing their own climate and sustainability challenges, which adds risk to the system. Food waste remains a major issue, both economically and environmentally. Most of it comes from households across the UK^v.

The Yorkshire and Humber region saw a 10% decrease in agricultural income from 2022-23^{vi}. Sustainable farming incentives provided opportunities for the industry to move towards approaches that improve energy efficiency and boost biodiversity, but this has recently been halted.

Changes to business rates, national insurance and rising costs will disproportionately impact smaller enterprise success in the food markets against larger, and global competitors.

“There are fine margins with producers going out of business; supermarkets are dominating and maximising for share-holders”

- North Yorkshire small food business

Our environment – Climate change is affecting the food system, with the biggest impacts seen in both UK food production and global markets. Extreme weather such as heatwaves, floods, droughts, plus soil erosion is especially concerning.

It’s not just farming that’s affected; the infrastructure that supports food distribution, storage, processing, and retail is also vulnerable to these events. As a result, we’re likely to see more fluctuations in supply, which could lead to rising food and product prices^{vii}.

The increasing frequency of extreme weather is putting soil health at serious risk, particularly through heavy rainfall and drought. Hotter, drier conditions make soil more vulnerable to wind erosion, while intense rain can wash it away.

According to the Environment Agency’s State of the Environment report^{viii}, around 4 million hectares of soil in England and Wales are at risk of becoming compacted, and over 2 million hectares are at risk of erosion.

This kind of soil degradation doesn’t just affect farming, it also increases the risk of flooding and threatens biodiversity, water quality, and the long-term fertility of the land^{ix}.

Climate change poses a serious threat to the food system, but at the same time, the food system itself is one of the biggest contributors to climate change and nature loss. In other words, it’s both affected by environmental pressures and a major driver of them^x.

Decarbonising the food system is especially challenging. When you include imported food, the UK’s food system is responsible for around 38% of the country’s total greenhouse gas emissions. Agriculture alone makes up nearly 12% of those emissions. Looking ahead to 2040, agriculture and aviation are expected to be the UK’s top sources of emissions.

The environmental impact of our food system stretches beyond UK borders. About 35% of the food we consume is imported, which means our choices also affect ecosystems and sustainability in other countries^{xi}.

The widespread use of pesticides and fertilisers has had a significant impact on biodiversity, particularly in agricultural landscapes. Pesticides, while effective at controlling pests, often harm non-target species such as pollinators, aquatic organisms, and beneficial insects, disrupting food webs and ecosystem functions. Fertilisers, especially nitrogen and phosphorus-based ones, can lead to nutrient runoff into nearby water bodies, causing eutrophication (an over-enrichment of water that depletes oxygen and leads to the death of aquatic life). These practices reduce habitat quality and diversity, leading to declines in species richness and abundance. Over time, this can result in the homogenisation of ecosystems, making them more vulnerable to climate change and other environmental stresses.

“Extreme weather is making farming harder and it’s the main threat to our food security. Farmers need support in preparing for and coping with droughts and floods.”

- Martin Lines, farmer and chief executive of the Nature Friendly Farming Network

Imagine the difference...

Imagine a future where North Yorkshire leads the way in building a food system that is healthy, fair, and sustainable for all. A system where fresh, nutritious food is accessible to every household - whether in a bustling market town or a remote rural village.

Where local farmers and producers thrive, supported by strong regional supply chains and communities that value seasonal, low-impact food. Where schools, hospitals, and care homes serve meals that nourish both people and planet.

In this vision, food waste is dramatically reduced, nature is restored through regenerative farming, and people are inspired to grow, cook, and care about where their food comes from.

Our health

- 1. Food justice and wellbeing:** Everyone has access to nutritious food, no matter where they live. Non-communicable diseases are prevented, and the burdens of diet-related illness are virtually eradicated.
- 2. Informed and engaged citizens:** People are well-informed about the food choices they make, celebrating where their food comes from, and choosing healthier options. Junk food marketing no longer influences our choice with nutritious food the easy choice.
- 3. Reconnection with nature:** People are reconnected with nature, the land, and the sea. Through schools, community food-growing spaces, and educational programmes, people have the skills and opportunity to grow and prepare their own food.

"...have a system that means people don't have to choose between quality food and something else."

- North Yorkshire community food project representative

Our economy

- 1. Celebration of heritage:** North Yorkshire's unique food heritage is celebrated and central to the food system. Independent and global businesses alike bring innovation to the table.
- 2. Sustained innovation:** Innovation is focused on people and planet as well as a fair profit. Technological innovation and regenerative practices help us to not only adapt to climate change but to take collective action to achieve resilient, carbon-negative food systems. Farms in the region are economically sustainable.
- 3. Connected, sustainable supplies:** Supply chain businesses are connected, food miles are reduced and local wealth and expertise are maintained and grow through public procurement practices, collaborative business, farm clusters and more farmer-focused cooperative working.

Our environment

- 1. Zero waste:** A circular economy is a smarter, more sustainable way of living and doing business. We encourage smart portions*, recycling, and food innovation to cut food waste down to almost nothing for the benefit of our community, businesses and the environment.
- 2. Effective land use:** We have a joined-up approach to land use that manages water, carbon storage, and biodiversity, all while maintaining food production. This will help create a more sustainable and balanced food system.
- 3. Thriving regenerative agriculture:** A growing system that works alongside nature to produce fresh, seasonal, nutritionally dense, affordable food for local communities and public procurers. This will help create commercial opportunities to export our expertise, supporting a thriving local economy.

*portion size that is nutritionally balanced, appropriately sized for individual needs, and mindful of health goals

Together we stand for

- Fairness, equality, and equity; health, wellbeing and enough food for all.
- The need to reconnect everybody with nature, land, sea and food.
- No waste.
- A self-supporting circular economy.
- Health and wellbeing for all.
- Nutritionally dense food from regenerative agricultural systems.
- A future where healthy food becomes the 'treat' rather than junk food.
- Enabling collaborative action.
- Understanding lived experience to inform better food system decisions.

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Our ingredients for change

When we saw the challenges in North Yorkshire's food system, we also saw the potential for food in North Yorkshire to become something radically different and we wanted to take action.

But we couldn't do it alone. So, a range of partners from across the system embarked on a process to understand how we could transform the North Yorkshire food system, using the Three Horizons framework^{xii} to guide us.

Where are we now?

- Understanding the current state of the system (H1)

Where do we want to be?

- Vision and values of a transformed food system for the future (H3)

How do we get there, collectively?

- Identifying actions to support transformation and avoid falling back to unsustainable patterns (H2+)

How will we know?

- Underpinned by transformation-focused governance and evaluation

A partnership approach to action

Food for the Future North Yorkshire is a collaboration. Strong partnerships are vital to ensure coordinated, self-reinforcing, system-wide action on food. The partnership is facilitated by North Yorkshire Council's Public Health team but the responsibility and accountability for action sits with all partners working in the food system.

Leadership is distributed which means we spread responsibility and decision-making across our partners, rather than relying on just one leader or a small group at the top. By sharing the load, trusting others, and working together we will make better decisions.

Using the Three Horizons approach we have collectively:

- Explored good practice from around the county.
- Developed a series of transformation-focused workshops to collectively understand our challenges and opportunities for change.
- Had conversations with a range of communities and organisations.
- Explored governance arrangements to consider how we will form ourselves to coordinate action.
- Developed an evaluation framework that helps us to plan and design for transformation-focused action, understand our impact, and reflect on our processes.

Our food system partners:

- Agri-tech representatives
- Community Dietician
- Community First Yorkshire
- Community Food Partnerships
- NYC Councillor
- DEFRA
- NYC Economic Development
- NYC Environment and climate
- FareShare Yorkshire
- FixOurFood Commission
- Food, Farming & Rural Network
- Good Food York
- Grow Yorkshire
- YNY Mayoral Combined Authority
- North Yorkshire National Parks
- NYC Planning Policy
- Professional evaluators
- NYC Public Health
- Regenerative farmers
- Rethink Food
- Small and medium-sized enterprises
- Soil Association
- Trading Standards
- University of York
- NYC Waste Services
- Yorkshire Agricultural Society
- NYC Youth Voice and Engagement

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What do people think?

As part of our exploration, we asked a range of people what they thought about the food system and what would enable us to have affordable, nutritious and sustainable food for all.

Let's Talk Food^{xiii} surveyed 2,053 people in North Yorkshire about how healthy their diet was, how accessible food was, and what affected food waste behaviour.

Key messages were:

 Lowering the cost of healthy food, reducing unhealthy food advertising and supporting local gardens or food projects are most likely to make it easier to get healthy food.

 Around a quarter of people throw away unused food once a week or more.

 Things making it difficult to reduce food waste are food going off and food being sold in larger amounts than needed - having skills and expertise to repurpose food and use leftovers are also key to reducing food waste.

For more detail, go to the 'Want to know more?' section of the framework on pg.25.

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Task Group Conversations with representatives from across the food system.

System actors recognise system challenges to include:

- Power imbalance between large globalised businesses and smaller local businesses.
- Major external influences such as climate change and adapting to them.
- Working through dilemmas arising from transformative change. E.G. Around emissions from food transport and implications of shifts towards more plant-based diets for the livestock sector. There may be unintended consequences and trade-offs and there will be existential challenges for some sectors.

System actors recognised future opportunity to include:

- A joined-up approach to land use and water management.
- Vibrant community food environments that are places of opportunity and wellbeing and supported by a commitment to locally oriented procurement.
- Education for ecological awareness and reconnection.
- High regional self-sufficiency.

Community Conversations with school children and youth councils, small to medium enterprises, community food partnerships and people with lived experience of food insecurity.

Key messages included:

- For some people, family traditions and connections are very strongly related to food.
- For some people, the basic needs of personal and community safety are a priority before consideration of food.
- Food spans from being a necessity, an ordinary part of life, to something that is protected and respected.
- Everyone's right to affordable, nutritious food should be respected.

- We need to have a food system that means people don't have to choose between quality food and something else.
- We need to feed our local communities with good food.
- Locally sourced procurement is important.

'People with a reasonable cash flow can do a weekly shop'

- Community Food Project representative

'Different people prioritise different things'

- Community Food Project representative

'I need to feel safe [in my neighbourhood] before I can think about food'

- Young person living in Scarborough

'People have less income over after paying rent'

- Community Food Project representative

'If only we could... feed the poorly and the homeless people'

- Key stage 3 pupil, Scarborough

'If only we could... treat food as a public good and respect everyone's right to affordable, nutritious food'

- Community Food Project representative

Our priority actions for transformation

Partners came together in November 2024 to identify what collective action we thought would make the most transformational change to the North Yorkshire food system. The actions below were chosen for their potential to:

- Positively disrupt the unsustainable status quo.
- Encourage deeper value-based shifts.
- Protect and grow innovation.
- Demonstrate additionality to what is already supporting positive change.
- Stimulate a system-wide change.

Parts of the system we are trying to change (the action domains)	Priority actions to support transformation
Secure affordable nutritious food for all - Tackling the root causes of food insecurity and creating the right conditions for everyone to have equal access to nutritious food, regardless of income, geography, disability or dependency.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connect local community food providers and set up local joint arrangements. 2. Implement a 'local sourcing' food procurement policy. 3. Improve awareness and knowledge of those in client public-facing roles in food insecurity issues.
Raise Yorkshire pride in food businesses - Celebrating and supporting a local food economy that prioritises local food products, connects food producers and food citizens, and progresses more self-reliant and resilient food networks. Putting good food entrepreneurs and enterprises at the heart of local economic development to ensure that buying local is the healthy and easy choice whilst also creating jobs, businesses and prosperity and regenerating high streets and local places.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop a North Yorkshire strategy for growth and development of holistic food/business approaches. 2. Establish a dynamic food purchasing system*.
Welcome innovation in food industry - Developing and utilising the emerging science and innovation in diet and nutrition to improve the nutritional quality of food produced for our food citizens.	
Shape local spaces for healthy food communities - Communities reaching their full potential to access land and capital assets to grow their own food or set up community spaces for making eating and sharing food, forming strong community connections and resilience. Food hubs being the centre of all communities and are the places to go for local, nutritious produce.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish 'know how to grow and cook' schemes in schools and communities. 2. Establish a county-wide community growing initiative.
Produce food with nature - Creating abundant spaces where people, plants and wildlife can thrive together to produce more food with better managed natural resources (including water, soil, and woodland). Promoting sustainable practices of land, ocean and freshwater management that improves biodiversity, regeneration and better captures and stores carbon.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Invest in farmer-led knowledge transfer about regenerative agriculture. 2. Introduce differential lending for regenerative farming investments. 3. Develop a public-facing campaign for direct action in food sustainability.
Create an eat well culture through valued nutritional education - Enabling and inspiring food citizens to have a better understanding of the nutritional value of healthier food and how we can experience this easily and affordably in our everyday lives; increasing self-efficacy, skills and motivation to prepare and consume nutritious food.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop and roll out a 'whole school approach to food'. 2. Embed Rethink Food's** 'high school ready' programme for Year 6 pupils.
Facilitate circular food economies - Encouraging regenerative food production and effective business solutions to reduce avoidable food loss, waste and pollution. Circulating products and materials (at their highest value) and regenerate nature. Removing linear 'take, make, waste' practices.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure stronger retail incentives for regenerative farming. 2. Support business clusters*** through investment and local planning.

*Dynamic purchasing systems offers a range of services that are searchable, allowing buyers to filter and engage with the suppliers that offer the relevant goods and services they are looking for. It also offers those services on largely preset contract terms making the procurement process more efficient ** High School Ready – Rethink Food – Food Education ***Business clusters are geographic concentration of interconnected businesses, suppliers, and associated institutions in a particular field.

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The future is happening now!

There are already lots of brilliant initiatives already supporting positive and transformative change in the North Yorkshire food system. We spotlight a few of these over the next few pages. There will be many more that we hope to identify, recognise and celebrate for their impact

Case Studies

North Yorkshire Rotters: Fighting Food Waste Through Education

Who they are

They are a volunteer-led group supported by North Yorkshire Council, dedicated to helping communities reduce food waste through hands-on education.

Where they work

Across North Yorkshire markets, schools and community events.

What they do

Engaging activities to spark change:

- Market stalls with food-saving tips.
- School workshops on waste and sustainability.
- Smoothie bikes for fun, healthy demos.

- Composting tutorials and wormery-making.
- Campaigns: Love Food Hate Waste, Home Composting, Beyond Carbon.

Why it matters

Food waste is a climate issue.

UK households throw away 7 million tonnes of food and drink every year.

North Yorkshire Rotters are transforming habits by:

Making sustainability fun and accessible, reaching all age groups and backgrounds, and supporting net-zero goals through education.

Want to Learn More?

[Home > North Yorkshire Rotters](#)

Holiday Activities and Food (HAF) programme: ensuring access to food and enrichment for children during school holidays

Programme name

Holiday Activities and Food (HAF), locally known as 'FEAST'

Where it operates

Nationwide across England, funded by the Department for Education (DfE). Locally, across North Yorkshire.

What it offers

Free meals and enriching activities for eligible children during main school holidays:

- Nutritious meals.
- Creative and physical activities.
- Cooking and food prep skills.
- Social and emotional development.

Who it's for

Children from Reception to Year 11, eligible for benefits-related free school meals

Why it's transformative

- Promotes equal access to nutritious food.
- Supports child health and wellbeing.
- Reduces the holiday experience gap for low-income families.

Want to learn more?

[What is FEAST - North Yorkshire Together](#)

Farming in Protected Landscapes programme

Jack and Laura Bell, Ingleby Farms, Arncliffe Hall, Ingleby Arncliffe

Ingleby Farms, owned by the Bell family, and contract farmed in partnership with Richard Pattison, is a 448ha estate comprising of a herd of 130 pedigree South Devon cows and 600 predominantly Lleyn sheep.

After engaging with a regenerative farming consultant and undertaking a carbon audit, they applied to the Farming in Protected Landscapes Programme (FiPL) for funding to help them: -

- Move towards a regeneratively grazed system.
- Reduce the farms carbon footprint from their livestock.
- Reduce leaching and sediment into Carr Beck.
- Address climate change and nature recovery through improving soil health and grass utilisation.

Their first project at Scarthwood Farm focused on re-establishing old field boundaries and introducing infrastructure to trial a move to a regenerative adaptive multi paddock grazing system for both cows and sheep.

This trial was very successful and further funding support enabled the system to be rolled out across the estate. The approach taken allows land to be rested for longer periods of time with grass being left to grow much longer.

This change to the grazing management system has led to better soil health and water holding capacity, increased wildlife and pasture diversity and healthier cattle. Lower costs have been achieved through a reduction in fertiliser use and bought in feed and straw through longer grazing periods and overwintering heifers on deferred grass.

Note: FiPL is a five-year Defra funded Programme (July 2021 to March 2026) running in all of the English National Parks and National Landscapes to help farmers and other land managers adapt to future changes in agricultural support.

Deliciously Yorkshire
Making Yorkshire the Food & Drink Capital of Britain

Who they are

A regional network dedicated to promoting, supporting, and developing Yorkshire’s independent food and drink businesses.

Where they work

Across Yorkshire from artisan producers in the Dales to city-based restaurants and breweries.

What they do

Deliciously Yorkshire champions local excellence by:

- Supporting artisan producers, farm shops, and delis.
- Promoting cafes, coffee shops, and restaurants.
- Celebrating breweries, hotels, and hospitality venues.
- Hosting the Taste Awards – the North’s largest food & drink accolades.
- Amplifying members through media, events, and campaigns.

“We respect tradition, encourage innovation, and celebrate great taste.”

Why it’s transformative

Strengthens local economies and rural livelihoods. Builds regional pride and identity. Encourages sustainable sourcing and food heritage. Connects producers with consumers through storytelling and visibility.

Working group

Good Food Businesses supporting ethical, independent producers and retailers across the region.

Learn more

[About Deliciously Yorkshire, who we are and what we do](#)

Communities of Practice – tackling food insecurity in North Yorkshire

Background

In 2023, the York and North Yorkshire Food Summit marked a turning point in regional efforts to understand and address food insecurity. Drawing on insights from the York and North Yorkshire Covid Recovery Insight Project: Food Insecurity, the summit catalysed a wave of collective action and innovation.

Following the summit, the Localities team in North Yorkshire launched a series of Community of Practice (CoP) sessions, open to all community food providers across the region. These sessions aimed to foster collaboration, share best practices, and explore sustainable models for food support.

Objectives

- Build a shared understanding of effective food support models.
- Strengthen individual and community resilience.
- Encourage collaboration among food providers across localities.
- Promote dignity-based approaches to food access.

Focus Areas

The five Community of Practice sessions centered around key themes identified through research and local experience:

Topic	Description
Place-Based Collaborative Models & Food Ladder	Encouraged integrated local partnerships and progressive support systems that help individuals move from crisis support to food independence.
More Than Food Models	Explored holistic services that combine food provision with mental health provision, social connection, and wraparound support.
Mixed Income Models	Investigated sustainable funding strategies that blend charitable support with income-generating activities.
Pantries & Give-As-You-Can Cafés	Highlighted inclusive, dignity-based models that allow individuals to contribute what they can while accessing nutritious food.

Outcomes

- Knowledge exchange: Providers shared lived experiences, challenges, and successes, enriching the collective understanding of food support strategies.
- Network building: New relationships formed across locality areas, leading to ongoing collaboration and peer support.
- Local action: Inspired by the sessions, several communities began meeting regularly to co-design and implement tailored food initiatives.
- Resilience strengthening: The models discussed have been shown to enhance both individual and community resilience, promoting long-term wellbeing.

The Communities of Practice initiative has proven to be a powerful mechanism for driving change in North Yorkshire’s food support landscape.

By creating space for dialogue, learning, and collaboration, the region is building a more resilient and equitable food system - one rooted in community strength and shared purpose.

How will we evaluate our progress?

Achieving transformation would not be possible without transforming our approach to evaluation.^{xiv xv}

Evaluation plays a vital role in understanding if we're on the right path in our journey and that we maintain a truly transformational ambition.

We've co-designed an evaluation framework for Food for the Future that recognises the complexity of food system change.

Evaluation for us means a continuous, iterative process of reflection, sense-making and judgement that underpins how we organise and make decisions.

Our evaluation framework helps us understand:

1. Whether we have the enabling conditions in place for an impactful action framework
2. What food system actions we should prioritise
3. What our impacts are on the North Yorkshire food system, and whether we're contributing to positive transformation
4. Our learning more broadly, particularly so we can share this with other like-minded organisations and initiatives.

Our framework also highlights the key goals and guides of our work, and the various kinds of feedback that will inform us about our progress and impact.

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Want to know more?

Click on the below to find out more about...

How we built the framework

For more information on Three Horizons workshop reports, transformation-focused evaluation and governance please email nypublichealth@northyorks.gov.uk

Policy drivers influencing our work

The National Food Strategy – The Plan:
An independent Review for the Government (2021)
[The National Food Strategy - The Plan](#)

A UK Government Food Strategy for England
[A UK government food strategy for England - GOV.UK](#)

York and North Yorkshire Combined Authority: Growth Plan (2025)
[Local Growth Plan work underway > Mayoral Combined Authority](#)

North Yorkshire Climate Change Strategy (2023 – 2030)
[Climate change strategy 2023 to 2030 | North Yorkshire Council](#)

Tackling obesity: Government strategy
[Tackling obesity: government strategy - GOV.UK](#)

Net Zero Strategy: Build Back Greener (2022)
[Net Zero Strategy: Build Back Greener - GOV.UK](#)

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Other useful links and websites....

FixOurFood – Transforming the Yorkshire food system
[Home - Fix Our Food](#)

The Food Foundation
[Home](#)

Family Resources Survey Department of Work and Pensions
[Family Resources Survey - GOV.UK](#)

Food, Farming and Countryside Commission: The food conversation
[Changing the conversation about food - Food, Farming and Countryside Commission](#)

Food Standards Agency
[Homepage | Food Standards Agency](#)

Healthwatch North Yorkshire's 'Ploughing through barriers: Understanding the challenges and promoting help-seeking in farming communities' report (2025)
[Ploughing through barriers | Healthwatch NorthYorkshire](#)

WRAP
[The Food Waste Reduction Roadmap: Progress Update 2024 | WRAP - The Waste and Resources Action Programme](#)

Love Food Hate Waste
[Love Food Hate Waste / Preventing food waste](#)

Glossary of terms

This glossary defines key concepts and terminology used throughout the Food for the Future framework.

Food system	The complete network involved in producing, processing, distributing, consuming, and disposing of food. It includes people, infrastructure, institutions, and policies.
Regenerative agriculture	A farming approach that restores and enhances soil health, biodiversity, and water cycles, aiming to produce food in harmony with natural ecosystems.
Circular economy	An economic model that minimises waste and maximises resource efficiency. In food systems, it involves practices such as composting, reuse, and reducing food loss.
Dynamic purchasing system (DPS)	A flexible procurement mechanism that allows public sector buyers to engage with approved suppliers offering relevant goods and services under pre-set contract terms.
Food citizenship	The concept that individuals are active participants in shaping the food system through their choices, advocacy, and community involvement. The term 'food citizen' treats people more than merely consumers.
Food insecurity	A condition in which individuals or households lack consistent access to sufficient, affordable, and nutritious food.
Whole school approach to food	An educational strategy that integrates food education across the curriculum, school meals, and community engagement to promote healthy eating and sustainability.
Climate anxiety	Emotional distress caused by concern over climate change and its impacts, particularly affecting younger generations.
Business clusters	Geographic concentrations of interconnected businesses, suppliers, and institutions within a specific sector, fostering collaboration and innovation.
Community food hubs	Local spaces where communities can grow, cook, share, and access nutritious food, strengthening social ties and resilience.
Farming in Protected Landscapes (FIPL)	A Defra-funded programme supporting farmers in National Parks and Areas of Outstanding Natural Beauty to improve environmental sustainability and adapt to climate challenges.
High School Ready programme	An initiative by Rethink Food designed to prepare Year 6 pupils for secondary school through food education and healthy lifestyle promotion.
Public procurement	The process by which public sector organisations purchase goods and services, such as food for schools and hospitals, with potential to support local economies and sustainability goals.
Land use	The management and allocation of land for agriculture, conservation, development, and other purposes, influencing food production and environmental outcomes.

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^v[United Kingdom Food Security Report 2024: Theme 2: UK Food Supply Sources - GOV.UK](#)

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